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New taxa of the subfamily Phaneropterinae (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae) from Africa: the tribes Otiaphysini and Preussiini

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Abstract. The new material on the following African genera of the subfamily Phaneropterinae is considered: *Drepanophyllum* Karsch, 1890 and *Tetraconcha* Karsch, 1890 belonging to the tribe Otiaphysini; *Enochletica* Karsch, 1896 and *Weissenbornia* Karsch, 1888 belonging to the tribe Preussiini. Four new species and two new subspecies are described: *Drepanophyllum irisovi* sp. n. (Cameroon), *Drepanophyllum corrosifolium ugandense* subsp. n. (Uganda), *Tetraconcha bicolor* sp. n. (Uganda), *Tetraconcha unicolor* sp. n. (Uganda), *Enochletica simulata* sp. n. (Uganda), and *Weissenbornia praestantissima aurea* subsp. n. (Uganda). All these species and subspecies are distinguished from each other and from all other representatives of the genera studied by the structure and colouration of their tegmina, as well as by some features of the stridulatory vein teeth, the shape of the male cerci and/or the structure of the male genital plate.

Key words: Phaneropterinae, Otiaphysini, Preussiini, *Drepanophyllum*, *Tetraconcha*, *Enochletica*, *Weissenbornia*, new taxa, Africa.

Новые таксоны подсемейства Phaneropterinae (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae) из Африки: трибы Otiaphysini и Preussiini

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Резюме. Рассмотрен новый материал по четырем следующим африканским родам подсемейства Phaneropterinae: *Drepanophyllum* Karsch, 1890 и *Tetraconcha* Karsch, 1890, принадлежащим к трибе Otiaphysini; *Enochletica* Karsch, 1896 и *Weissenbornia* Karsch, 1888, принадлежащим к трибе Preussiini. Описаны четыре новых вида и два новых подвида: *Drepanophyllum irisovi* sp. n. (Камерун), *Drepanophyllum corrosifolium ugandense* subsp. n. (Уганда), *Tetraconcha bicolor* sp. n. (Уганда), *Tetraconcha unicolor* sp. n. (Уганда), *Enochletica simulata* sp. n. (Уганда) и *Weissenbornia praestantissima aurea* subsp. n. (Уганда). Все эти виды и подвиды отличаются друг от друга и от всех остальных представителей рассматриваемых родов строением и окраской надкрылий, а также некоторыми особенностями зубчиков стридуляционной жилки, формой церок самца и/или строением генитальной пластинки самца.

Ключевые слова: Phaneropterinae, Otiaphysini, Preussiini, *Drepanophyllum*, *Tetraconcha*, *Enochletica*, *Weissenbornia*, новые таксоны, Африка.

Introduction

This paper is devoted to the taxonomy of katydids from four genera of the African tribes Otiaphysini Karsch, 1889 and Preussiini Karsch, 1890, belonging to the subfamily Phaneropterinae: *Drepanophyllum* Karsch, 1890, *Tetraconcha* Karsch, 1890, *Enochletica* Karsch, 1896, *Weissenbornia* Karsch, 1888. All these tribes and genera as well as a significant part of their species were described by the outstanding investigator of the African Tettigoniidae, Dr F. Karsch [1888, 1889, 1890a, b, 1896]. Recently, our knowledge on some of these taxa has been greatly expanded in the publications of Dr B. Massa [2017, 2021, etc.]. However, my research of new material on these exotic forest groups of Tettigoniidae showed that they are still insufficiently studied and contain interesting new taxa, which are described here.

Material and methods

The study is based on the material (including types of new taxa) deposited at the Zoological Institute of the

Russian Academy of Sciences (ZIN, St Petersburg, Russia). This material is dry and pinned; it was collected by the Russian researchers in some countries of the Afrotropical Region.

Tribe Otiaphysini Karsch, 1889 *Drepanophyllum irisovi* Gorochov, sp. n. (Figs 1–8)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Cameroon, border of South and East regions, Dja Reserve on Dja River, ~600 m, secondary forest near river, on leave of bush at daytime, 15–22.02.2016 (A.V. Gorochov). Paratypes: 1♂, 1♀ (ZIN), same data as for holotype.

Description. Male (holotype). General appearance (Fig. 1) similar to that of *D. corrosifolium* Karsch, 1896 but with following pattern: head light brown with slightly lighter (almost yellowish) most part of clypeus and of labrum as well as large area under both rostrum and antennal cavities, with brown scape and border of antennal cavity as well as most part of maxillary palpus and spots on head dorsum, with dark brown pedicel and partly antennal flagellum as well as spots on greyish eyes, and with rose anterior surface of upper rostral tubercle as well as yellowish ocelli and rest of antennal flagellum; pronotum yellowish with brown to light brown lateral lobes and hind part of disc, and with thin dark brown border around all pronotal edges; legs also yellowish with dark

Figs 1–14. Species of the genus *Drepanophyllum*, general view and details of structure.

1–8 – *D. irisovi* sp. n.; 9–11 – *D. corrosifolium ugandense* subsp. n.; 12–13 – *D. marmoratum*; 14 – *D. c. corrosifolium*, syntype. 1 – male, dorsal view; 2, 12 – female, lateral view; 3–4 – stridulatory apparatus: 3 – of left male tegmen, 4 – of right male tegmen; 5, 10 – male abdominal apex from above and slightly behind; 6, 11 – stridulatory vein of male left tegmen ventrally; 7 – female abdominal apex from side; 8 – female genital plate from below; 9 – male left tegmen; 13–14 – male right cercus from more or less above. 12 – after Brunner-Wattenwyl [1891]; 13–14 – after Cigliano et al. [2022].

Рис. 1–14. Виды рода *Drepanophyllum*, общий вид и детали строения.

1–8 – *D. irisovi* sp. n.; 9–11 – *D. corrosifolium ugandense* subsp. n.; 12–13 – *D. marmoratum*; 14 – *D. c. corrosifolium*, синтип. 1 – самец, вид сверху; 2, 12 – самка, вид сбоку; 3–4 – стридуляционный аппарат: 3 – левого надкрылья самца, 4 – правого надкрылья самца; 5, 10 – вершина брюшка самца сверху и слегка сзади; 6, 11 – стридуляционная жилка левого надкрылья самца вентрально; 7 – вершина брюшка самки сбоку; 8 – генитальная пластинка самки снизу; 9 – левое надкрылье самца; 13–14 – правый церк самца более или менее сверху. 12 – по [Brunner-Wattenwyl, 1891]; 13–14 – по [Cigliano et al., 2022].

brown coxae and trochanters as well as small basal part of hind femur, with brown distal parts of all femora and proximal parts of all tibiae as well as long distoventral area on hind tibia and lateral marks on all tarsi, and with almost light brown rest of tibiae and of tarsi; tegmina uniformly brown with yellowish to rose most part of venation (Fig. 1), large yellowish spot on stridulatory apparatus of left tegmen (Fig. 3), contrasting colouration of such apparatus in right tegmen (its venation yellowish, but membranes dark brown; Fig. 4), and without any transparent or semitransparent spots and areas on lateral field (Fig. 1); hind wings transparent with brown apical part and light brown to rose venation in rest part (Fig. 1); pterothorax brown to light brown with reddish brown dorsal part; abdomen yellowish to light brown with brown areas on apical and subapical tergites as well as on all sternites, and with dark brown

cerci and genital plate as well as distal part of epiproct (Fig. 5). Upper rostral tubercle rather high; its narrow and vertically truncated anterior part (having thin anteromedian groove) about 0.8 mm in height, with almost straight anterior edge in profile, and separated from strongly reduced lower rostral tubercle by moderately narrow concave area (width of this area between antennal cavities almost 0.5 mm). Tegmina moderately wide, with most widened part of tegmen located not far from tegminal apex and with costal area in distal half of tegmen rather narrow (width of tegmen in point of RS bifurcation ~8 mm and in most widened place ~10.5 mm; length of tegminal part before latter place ~30 mm and after it ~7 mm); stridulatory apparatus as in Figs 3, 4; stridulatory vein of left tegmen rather wide, with 78 or 79 rather long stridulatory teeth (six medial teeth located more sparse

and forming distinctly curved part of this vein; Fig. 6), and with 27 teeth in 1 mm of middle part of this vein. Last abdominal tergite with slightly concave posteromedian edge; epiproct moderately short but rather wide, almost rectangular (widely truncated at apex; Fig. 5); cercus very short and thick, arcuate (moderately curved medially) and with acute and almost spine-like apical hook (Fig. 5); genital plate approximately 1.5 times as long as cercus, elongate, slightly narrowing from basal part to distal third and with more narrowed distal part having small (narrow) but rather deep notch at apex (Fig. 5); genitalia membranous.

Variability. Second male (paratype) with light brown area under rostrum and antennae, rose tinge on clypeus, brown spot at base of labrum, and completely light brown subapical abdominal tergite, but without reddish tinge on dorsal part of pterothorax.

Female. Colouration and structure of body distinguished from those of males of this species by following characters: head as in holotype but with a pair of small rose marks under antennal cavities; pronotum with lighter (almost yellowish) band on each lateral lobe along dark ventral border; legs also with lighter (light brown with brown marks) coxae and trochanters; tegmina spotted, with some rather large spots greyish (semitransparent) and lacking venation (row of such spots in costal area, large group of similar spots along anal tegminal edge near point of RS bifurcation, and also similar but smaller and more distal spots scattered between branches of R), as well as with larger reddish spot in proximal part of costal area (Fig. 2); rest of body with yellowish to light brown pterothorax, light brown to brown abdominal sternites, brown to dark brown three last abdominal tergites and epiproct as well as genital plate and ovipositor, and dark brown cerci (Fig. 7); dorsal tegminal fields lacking stridulatory apparatus; last abdominal tergite with semimembranous posteromedian part having almost straight posterior edge; epiproct similar to that of male but with posteromedian part having short and roundly angular projection; genital plate as in Fig. 8 and partly compressed laterally (Fig. 7). Strongly reduced ovipositor with a few small denticles in apical parts of dorsal and ventral valves (Fig. 7).

Length (in mm). Body: male 22–23, female 24; body with wings: male 48–50, female 49; pronotum: male 4.9–5.1, female 4.4; tegmina: male 37–38.5, female 36; hind femora: male 28–29, female 29; ovipositor (from base to apex) 2.6.

Comparison. This species is most similar in colouration and tegminal shape to *D. corrosifolium* described from another region of Cameroon, but it is distinguished from the latter species by distinctly shorter and thicker male cerci (compare Figs 5 and 14), as well as by the absence of any transparent and semitransparent areas and spots in the male tegminal lateral field (the male syntype of *D. corrosifolium* has a few such spots; see its photograph in Cigliano et al. [2022]). From *D. marmoratum* Karsch, 1890 also described from Cameroon, the new species differs in the male tegminal lateral field lacking any distinct semitransparent or transparent areas, and in the tegmina of both sexes narrower and with the most widened tegminal part located distinctly less far from the tegminal apex: the ratios of tegminal length to tegminal width in the point of RS bifurcation and in the widest part are 4.7–5.2 and 3.5–3.7 for *D. irisovi* sp. n. but 4–4.3 and 2.8–3.3 for *D. marmoratum*, respectively; the ratios of tegminal length to distance between the widest tegminal part and the tegminal apex are 5.2–5.7 for *D. irisovi* sp. n. and 3.4–3.8 for *D. marmoratum* (*D. marmoratum* has been measured after photographs in Cigliano et al. [2022], including those for the female holotypes of this species and of its synonym *Karschia corrosa* Brunner-Wattenwyl, 1891; the latter female is in accordance to all species characters

of *D. marmoratum*); additionally, the new species is distinguished from *D. marmoratum* by the femoral colouration yellowish with darkened apical parts (vs this colouration is more or less uniformly brown), the costal and interradiial tegminal areas in the point of RS bifurcation much narrower (Figs 2, 12), and the male cerci less strongly curved (Figs 5, 13). From the third species of this genus (*D. furcatum* Ragge, 1962, Uganda) the new species clearly differs in a very different (not almost uniformly greenish) colouration and another structure of the tegminal stridulatory apparatus (mirror and thickened chord in the right tegmen are distinctly shorter).

Etymology. This species is named in memory of Grigory Irisov, my friend and field companion during our trips to Cameroon and Uganda.

Drepanophyllum corrosifolium ugandense

Gorochov, **subsp. n.**

(Figs 9–11)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Uganda, southwestern part, Kanungu Distr., environs of Bwindi National Park, ~1500 m, secondary forest, at light, 19–22.02.2020 (A.V. Gorochov).

Description. Male (holotype). Body colouration very similar to that in *D. irisovi* sp. n. but with the following differences: head and pronotum more similar in colouration to those of male paratype of this species, but mouthparts (including maxillary palpi) completely yellowish, and hind part of pronotal disc also lighter (yellowish with greyish tinge); colouration of wings distinguished from that of *D. irisovi* sp. n. males only by larger yellowish spot on dorsal field of left tegmen (this spot including proximal half of mirror; but in *D. irisovi* sp. n., this mirror almost completely brown); legs distinguished from those of this species only by darker (completely brown) fore femur; rest of body approximately as in male paratype of *D. irisovi* sp. n. in colouration, but abdominal sternites and proximal two thirds of genital plate light brown. Structure of body also similar to that of this species, but some characteristic features presented: upper rostral tubercle slightly lower than in this species; its truncated anterior part (having thin anteromedian groove) about 0.6 mm in height, with small but distinct ventral tubercle directed forwards, and with narrower concave area between upper and lower rostral tubercles (width of this area between antennal cavities almost 0.3 mm); tegmina slightly narrower in middle part (compare Figs 1 and 9) and with tegminal stridulatory apparatus almost indistinguishable from that of nominotypical subspecies and of *D. irisovi* sp. n., but this apparatus in right tegmen with minimal transverse width of heavily sclerotized part between plectrum and mirror membrane almost 1.1 times as great as transverse width of nearest part of this membrane (vs this ratio ~0.9 in *D. c. corrosifolium* and ~1 in *D. irisovi* sp. n.), and in left tegmen with stridulatory vein slightly narrower and having shorter as well as more numerous and denser stridulatory teeth (1 mm of middle part of this vein with 35 teeth, and medial part of this vein less curved and with 3 or 4 barely sparser teeth; Fig. 11); abdominal apex also almost indistinguishable from that of *D. irisovi* sp. n., but cercus before apical part as in nominotypical subspecies (i.e. distinctly longer and thinner than in *D. irisovi* sp. n.) as well as with apical part more thin and acute than in *D. c. corrosifolium* (Figs 10, 14), and genital plate with very short and rounded apical notch (Fig. 10).

Female unknown.

Length (in mm). Body 19; body with wings 48; pronotum 4.3; tegmina 38; hind femora 28.5.

Comparison. The new subspecies is known from a significantly more eastern part of Africa and differs from the nominotypical subspecies (Cameroon) in the absence

of any transparent or semitransparent spots in the male tegminal lateral fields, a partly yellowish mirror in the left tegmen (vs this mirror completely dark), the above-mentioned (in the subspecies description) details of the stridulatory apparatus in the right tegmen, and the male cercus with a thinner and sharper apex; also it is useful to note that the male syntype of *D. c. corrosifolium*, judging by photographs from Cigliano et al. [2022], possibly has its epiproct with a narrowly rounded (not widely truncated) apex, and if it is not an epiproctal deformity, this new taxon may be a separate species but not a subspecies of *D. corrosifolium*. From all other congeners, the new subspecies is distinguished by the characters listed in its description (from *D. irisovi* sp. n.) or by the same characters as *D. irisovi* sp. n. (see the comparison after the description of this species).

Etymology. The new subspecies is named after the country Uganda where it was collected.

Tetraconcha bicolor Gorochov, sp. n.
(Figs 15–21)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Uganda, southwestern region, Bushenyi Distr., environs of Kalinzu Nature Reserve, ~1000 m, primary forest, at light, 23–28.02.2020 (A.V. Gorochov). Paratypes: 2♂ (ZIN), same data as for holotype.

Description. Male (holotype). Body distinctly smaller than in *Drepanophyllum irisovi* sp. n. Colouration yellowish with following pattern: epicranium rose with reddish brown spots on dorsum (a pair of spots near eyes and median spot on upper rostral tubercle and near it) and spot on each gena, yellowish ocelli and vertical stripe under each eye as well as small spot on ventromedial edge of each antennal cavity and triangular median spot near clypeus; antenna reddish brown to brown with yellowish base of scape and very small marks on middle and distal parts of flagellum; mouthparts with rose most part of palpi, tinge on mandibles, dorsal spot on clypeus and dorsal half of labrum; pronotum with numerous rose dots on disc and on lateral lobes; tegmina with brownish rose most part of lateral field between costal area and anal edge, brownish grey some cell membranes in basal part of yellowish costal area (Fig. 17), greyish (semitransparent) areas between R and dorsal field near its stridulatory apparatus as well as in dorsal field behind mirror (part of latter area short in left tegmen but almost twice larger in right tegmen; Figs 15, 16), brown to dark brown large spot on stridulatory apparatus of left tegmen (this spot including most part of stridulatory vein and of nearest vein as well as part of mirror membrane; Fig. 15), reddish brown basal area in both tegmina and stridulatory vein in right tegmen, and almost transparent mirror and small area near plectrum in latter tegmen (Fig. 16); hind wing transparent with brownish rose venation and thickened apical part (Fig. 18); legs rose to light reddish brown with yellowish proximal half of hind femur and ventral parts of three proximal segments of all tarsi. Upper rostral tubercle strongly truncated distally (lateral ocelli located practically at apex of this tubercle), with not narrowed anterior part having distinct median groove, without groove on dorsum, but with dorsal edges of lateral ocelli slightly and roundly projected upwards. Pronotum with slight median groove and V-shaped groove on disc, with posterior edge of disc barely rounded, and with lateral lobes rounded ventrally and posteroventrally but having rather deep and moderately wide (roundly angular) humeral notches. Tegmina long, with rather narrow and rounded distal parts, with stridulatory apparatus as in Figs 15 and 16, and with stridulatory vein of left tegmen regularly arcuate and having two lateral stridulatory teeth which larger and clearly sparser than others (Fig. 21); hind wing distinctly protruding beyond tegminal apices, with costal part as

in Fig. 18. Last abdominal tergite with barely but widely concave posteromedian edge; epiproct rather wide and short, almost rectangular and with distal part more or less straight and slightly curved upwards (Fig. 20); cercus rather long, moderately arcuate and with thin distal half having heavily sclerotized (darkened) small apical part which truncated at apex and with very small medial denticle (Figs 19, 20); genital plate moderately elongate, with rather wide proximal two thirds and narrow distal third having rather deep posteromedian notch and a pair of finger-like lobules around it (Fig. 20); genitalia membranous.

Variability. Paratypes with slightly lighter anterior part of head (this part almost completely or only clypeus and mandibles uniformly yellowish), sometimes without rose dots on pronotum and abdomen, and sometimes with completely darkened mirror of left tegmen and partly darkened mirror of right tegmen.

Female unknown.

Length (in mm). Body 15–17; body with wings 42–44; pronotum 4.8–5; tegmina 32.5–34; hind femora 22.5–23.5.

Comparison. The new species is most similar to *T. banzyvilliana* Griffini, 1909 (Zaire) but distinguished by the costal tegminal area almost completely yellowish (vs this area is very dark in the proximal half and yellowish in the distal half), the rest of the lateral tegminal field lighter (vs it is dark brown to blackish), the presence of a rather large greyish (semitransparent) area in the latter field near its stridulatory apparatus (vs this tegminal region with dark membranes), and clearly longer both the widened part of the dorsal field of the left tegmen and its mirror (compare Fig. 15 and the photograph of *T. banzyvilliana* holotype in Cigliano et al. [2022]). From all other congeners including “smaragdina-group” [Massa, 2017, 2021], *T. bicolor* sp. n. differs in the following combination of characters: tegminal colouration is bicolourous; left tegmen has a darker spot on its stridulatory apparatus and a normally developed (not almost indistinct or strongly modified) mirror; stridulatory vein of this tegmen is shorter or longer as well as regularly arcuate (not S-shaped or almost broken) and with only two lateral teeth which are distinctly larger and sparser than other teeth.

Etymology. This species name is the Latin word “bicolor” (two-colour, dichrome) due to the characteristic colouration of the tegmina.

Tetraconcha unicolor Gorochov, sp. n.
(Figs 22–28)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Uganda, western region, Kibale Distr., Kibale Biological Station of “MakerSU”, 0°33'68"N / 30°21'42"W, 1511 m, forest, 19–24.10.2014 (V.V. Anikin).

Description. Male (holotype). General appearance more or less similar to that of *T. bicolor* sp. n., but following differences presented: body colouration more uniformly yellowish (possibly greenish in living condition) with light brown antennal flagellum and area on pedicel as well as most part of fore and middle tibiae and tarsi, rose median ocellus and rather sparse dots on lateral and hind lobes of probotum as well as on most part of all femora (but distal femoral parts with brownish rose and distinctly denser dots), brownish grey eyes and a pair of small marks on dorsal borders of lateral ocelli, brown all membranes in distal part of tegminal costal area as well as in most part of dorsal field (but widened part of this field light brown in right tegmen and partly greyish brown in left one, and lateral tegminal field with distinct group of greyish brown membranes near stridulatory apparatus; Figs 22, 25, 26), and transparent hind wing having yellowish apical part and yellowish rose rest of venation (Fig. 23); structure of tegminal

Figs 15–28. Species of the genus *Tetraconcha*, males, details of structure.

15–21 – *T. bicolor* sp. n.; 22–28 – *T. unicolor* sp. n. 15, 25 – stridulatory apparatus of left tegmen; 16, 26 – stridulatory apparatus of right tegmen; 17, 22 – left tegmen; 18, 23 – costal part of left hind wing; 19, 24 – cercal apex from above; 20, 27 – abdominal apex from above and slightly behind; 21, 28 – stridulatory vein of left tegmen ventrally.

Рис. 15–28. Виды рода *Tetraconcha*, самцы, детали строения.

15–21 – *T. bicolor* sp. n.; 22–28 – *T. unicolor* sp. n. 15, 25 – стридуляционный аппарат левого надкрылья; 16, 26 – стридуляционный аппарат правого надкрылья; 17, 22 – левое надкрылье; 18, 23 – костальная часть левого заднего крыла; 19, 24 – вершина церка сверху; 20, 27 – вершина брюшка сверху и слегка сзади; 21, 28 – стридуляционная жилка левого надкрылья вентрально.

stridulatory apparatus as in Figs 25 and 26, with stridulatory vein of left tegmen slightly more arcuate than in *T. bicolor* sp. n. but having almost straight sublateral part which provided with a few teeth larger and sparser than others (three of these larger teeth largest and most sparse; Fig. 28); costal part of hind wing as in Fig. 23; abdominal apex similar to that of *T. bicolor* sp. n., but epiproct probably shorter or deformed (strongly retracted under last tergite), cercus with slightly more hooked distal portion having its heavily sclerotized (darkened) small apical part almost denticle-

like (Figs 24, 27), and genital plate with somewhat less narrow distal third and posteromedian notch (Fig. 27).

Female unknown.

Length (in mm). Body 14.7; body with wings 43; pronotum 4; tegmina 33; hind femora 22.

Comparison. The new species differs from *T. bicolor* sp. n. in a more uniform colouration of the tegmina, a different structure of the stridulatory teeth of the left tegmen, and some other small details listed

Figs 29–38. Species of the genera *Enochletica* and *Weissenbornia*, males, general view and details of structure.
 29–33 – *E. simulata* sp. n.; 34–35 – *E. ostentatrix*; 36–38 – *W. praestantissima aurea* subsp. n. 29, 36 – male, dorsal view; 30–31 – stridulatory apparatus: 30 – of left tegmen, 31 – of right tegmen; 32, 34, 38 – abdominal apex from above and slightly behind; 33, 35, 37 – stridulatory vein of left tegmen ventrally.

Рис. 29–38. Виды родов *Enochletica* и *Weissenbornia*, самцы, общий вид и детали строения.

29–33 – *E. simulata* sp. n.; 34–35 – *E. ostentatrix*; 36–38 – *W. praestantissima aurea* subsp. n. 29, 36 – самец, вид сверху; 30–31 – стридуляционный аппарат: 30 – левого надкрылья, 31 – правого надкрылья; 32, 34, 38 – вершина брюшка сверху и слегка сзади; 33, 35, 37 – стридуляционная жилка левого надкрылья вентрально.

above (in the description). From *T. loubesi* Massa, 2017, *T. morettoii* Massa, 2017 and *T. fusca* Massa, 2021 having more or less similar colouration of body and the structure of these teeth, *T. unicolor* sp. n. is distinguished by the widened part of the dorsal tegminal field less projecting medially (from *T. loubesi*), by this tegminal part longer (from *T. morettoii*), by a narrower posteromedian notch of the male genital plate (from both these species), and by a not S-shaped ventral part of the stridulatory vein in the left tegmen (from *T. fusca*). From all other congeners, it differs in the characteristic structure of stridulatory teeth (a few sublateral teeth are clearly larger and sparser than others) and in the same characters as *T. bicolor* sp. n. (except for the tegminal colouration and the structure of stridulatory teeth), and additionally from *T. banzyvilliana* and *T. perezii* Massa, 2017, in a less dark colouration of the tegminal lateral field.

Etymology. This species name is the Latin word “unicolor” (one-colour, monochrome) due to the general colouration of the tegmina.

Tribe Preussiini Karsch, 1890

Enochletica simulata Gorochov, sp. n. (Figs 29–33)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Uganda, western region, Karabole Distr., environs of Kibale National Park, ~1500 m, secondary forest, at light, 6–11.03.2020 (A.V. Gorochov). Paratype: 1♂ (ZIN), same data as for holotype.

Description. Male (holotype). Body colouration (Fig. 29) very similar to that of *E. ostentatrix* Karsch, 1896 from Cameroon: head yellowish with brown genae as well as areas between antennal cavities and lateral parts of clypeus, two light brownish rose short median longitudinal stripes on dorsum, dark brown to brown middle and distal parts of antennal flagellum, dark brown (almost blackish) palpi, light brown rest of mouthparts (but with darker dorsal marks on clypeus and labrum) and rather numerous small spots on rest of antenna; pronotum reddish brown with brownish rose disc having a pair of yellowish stripes along lateral edges and three barely distinct lightish longitudinal lines between them; tegmina light brown to almost yellowish with brown, light brown, reddish brown and greyish spots (Figs 29–31); hind wing darkened (almost dark grey) but with short yellowish subapical and small light brown to brown apical parts (Fig. 29); legs reddish brown with barely darker fore tibia, light brown fore and middle tarsi (having dark brown marks), and almost completely dark brown hind tarsus (but ventral parts of three proximal segments of all tarsi light); rest of thorax from greyish brown dorsally to reddish brown laterally and ventrally; abdomen dark brown with brown dorsum of anterior tergites, reddish brown sternites (having darker spots), and reddish brown to light brown small areas near these sternites as well as most part of cercus (but its distal part slightly darker) and proximal half of genital plate (Fig. 32). External structure of body distinguished from that of *E. ostentatrix* only by stridulatory vein of left tegmen with clearly denser stridulatory teeth ventrally (1 mm of this vein in its middle part with 28 teeth; Fig. 33), and genital plate with wider apical part having shorter styles and posteromedian notch (width of this apical part ~1.3 times as great as length of each style; Fig. 32); genitalia membranous.

Variability. Paratype with barely wider distal part of mirror in both tegmina and slightly narrower apical part of genital plate (width of this apical part ~1.1 times as great as length of each style) as well as even less deep posteromedian notch of genital plate, and without reddish or rose tinge on all body parts.

Female unknown.

Length (in mm). Body 18–20; body with wings 43–44; pronotum 7.5–8; tegmina 37–38; hind femora 13.5–14.

Comparison. The new species is almost indistinguishable from *E. ostentatrix* (previously the only representative of this genus [Massa, 2013]) in general appearance but with distinctly denser stridulatory teeth of the left tegmen (1 mm of the middle part of stridulatory vein has about 28 teeth in *E. simulata* sp. n. and about 17 teeth in *E. ostentatrix*; compare Figs 33 and 35) as well as a wider apical part of the male genital plate and shorter styles (width of this apical part is about 1.1–1.3 times as great as length of each style in *E. simulata* sp. n., but this ratio is about 0.6–0.7 in *E. ostentatrix*; see Figs 32 and 34).

Etymology. This species name is the Latin word “simulata” (simulating, imitating) due to the similarity of the new species with *E. ostentatrix*.

Weissenbornia praestantissima aurea

Gorochov, subsp. n.

(Figs 36–38)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): Uganda, western region, Karabole Distr., environs of Kibale National Park, ~1500 m, secondary forest, at light, 6–11.03.2020 (A.V. Gorochov).

Description. Male (holotype). General appearance (Fig. 36) very similar to that of nominotypical subspecies, but body colouration with following differences: labrum yellowish rose, strongly widened part of maxillary palpus light brown, tegmina yellowish with mostly light brown pattern (vs labrum and widened part of maxillary palpus intensively brown, and tegminal pattern dark brown to blackish). External structure of body almost identical to that of *W. p. praestantissima* Karsch, 1888 but having some characteristic features: stridulatory vein of left tegmen with ventral teeth as in Fig. 37 (1 mm of middle part of this vein with 31 stridulatory teeth); abdominal apex (Fig. 38) with straight (not slightly concave) posterodorsal edge of last tergite, somewhat more curved cerci, and clearly shorter posteromedian notch of genital plate (each style of latter plate approximately trice as long as this notch; in nominotypical subspecies, style almost twice as long as this notch); genitalia membranous.

Female unknown.

Length (in mm). Body 19; body with wings 38; pronotum 5.8; tegmina 30; hind femora 14.5.

Comparison. Differences between the new subspecies and *E. p. praestantissima* from Cameroon are listed above, in the description.

Etymology. This subspecies name is the Latin word “aurea” (golden) due to the characteristic body colouration.

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